

SECTION E

LANGUAGE

DIALECTAL HABITS AND SPEECH ERRORS IN SPOKEN FRENCH: THE IBIBIO LANGUAGE EXAMPLE

By

Miriam Stephen Inegbe, M.A.

misteve45@yahoo.com

+234 803 792 8319/+234 807 645 8851

Abstract

The goals of communication cannot be achieved without language. Language is therefore actively involved in human beings daily activities. This paper investigates the relevance of phonology in the instruction and learning of French by native Ibibio speakers. This work's emphasis is on the sound level of French as used by native Ibibio speakers. The sound system of Ibibio, one of the African languages spoken in South - Eastern Nigeria, how interferes and impedes effective communication using French by native Ibibio speakers. Thus, this paper recommends that the language instructor should focus more on the variations in the French of the native Ibibio speakers in order to achieve a near standard French by the Ibibio speakers of French.

Introduction

Several theoretical positions have been advanced by various scholars and linguists to explain the cause or causes of dialectal interferences on foreign languages by the native speakers of these languages.

Avram Noam Chomsky holds that language is an innate faculty, and as such every child is born with a set of rules and innate ability to acquire language as soon as the child is exposed to a language experience

(Chomsky, 1997). Burrhus Frederic Skinner maintains that children imitate the language of their environment. Imitation therefore is an important factor in language learning. Thus, language learning basically starts from the speaker's home. The learner right from his/her formative years has used his/her innate ability to acquire and imitate how his/her native dialect is spoken and is acquainted to the usual native sounds system. These native sounds exert some inhibitive influence on the native Ibibio French speakers, due to either the differences or similarities in Ibibio and French sound systems respectively. This agrees with Hult and Howard's, (2006) assertion that all languages consist of a set of abstract symbols - sounds, letters, numbers, elements of sign language... and a system for rules combining those symbols into larger units. The speakers (native Ibibio), due to how the Ibibio sounds are realized, transfer these same features to the spoken French. Consequently Ekah (2000) affirms that assertion;

the speaker, in the process of learning the language, mixes up certain codes and consistently fails to differentiate one sound from the other, the phonetic and the graphological features and subsequently the use of the one word for the other. This mix and the problem of interference are observed in students speech...

Interaction and dialoguing with the native Ibibio French speakers reveal the differences between the types of French spoken and the varieties spoken. This observation has led some linguists to claim that there is "Français d' Afrique" (David, 1974). This work sets out to examine the French and Ibibio phonemic inventories so as to determine the exact situation of phonological facilitation, dialectal habits and speech errors in spoken French by the native Ibibio French speaker.

The Ibibio and Ibibio Language

Ibibio language is spoken by the ibibio living in Akwa Ibom State of Nigeria in the following Local Government Areas as listed by Urua (2000): "Uyo, Itu, Uruan, Etinan, Nsit - Ibom. Nsit Atai, Nsit Ubium, Ibesikpo - Asutan, Ikono, Ini, Ikot - Abasi, Mkpat - Enin, Ibiono - Ibom,

Onna and Eket. Ibibio language belongs to the Cross River division of the Niger – Congo language family (Greenberg, 1963).

Phonological Segments of French and Ibibio Languages

A speaker of French as a second or third language needs the knowledge of the phonological components of the language to be able to assign right phonetic interpretations to French words so as to avoid dialectal habits and interference during oral articulation of French words since "words are made up not of letters but of functional sound units or phonemes" Henry Sweet (1845-1912) in Ong, (1982).

For a proper analysis of dialectal habit and speech errors in spoken French, it is necessary to attempt a comparison of the phonological systems of the French and Ibibio languages respectively. Meanwhile it is necessary to explain what phonology is. Phonology is an aspect of linguistics that studies the speech sounds of any language. Linguistic itself is defined by Lavenda and Schultz (1921) as a study that involves a search for patterns in the way speakers use language. They further explain that phonology examines individual languages to discover the particular sound combinations they contain and the patterns into which those sound combinations are organized.

There are two phonological systems, one corresponding to a phonemic version of the phonetic input and the other corresponding to the phonemic version of the orthography of the word (Perre *et al*, 2009). The phonemic inventory of a language involves a selection of significant speech sounds which the human organs can produce.

The French language has twenty consonantal sounds; six occlusives, fourteen constrictives in which six are fricatives and eight are sonantes (ALO', 1999). The French consonantal sounds include:

$$\left| \begin{array}{l} p, b, t, d, k, g, f, v. \\ s, z, \int, \square, m, n, m, n, \\ i, j, w, R \end{array} \right|$$

There are sixteen vowel sounds in French. These vowels are classified into oral vowels and nasal vowels. These vowel sounds according to ALO (1999) include:

i, e, ɛ, a, ɑ, ə, o, u, y,

ø, œ, æ, é, ã, ɜ, ɛ̃

The Ibibio phonemic inventory as identified by Simmons (1957) has fourteen Ibibio consonant sounds:

/b, p, kp, d, t, k, m, n, ɲ, f, s, h, w, y/;

Kaufman (1985) identified seventeen Ibibio consonant sounds;

/p, b, t, d, k, g, kp, f, s, m, n, ɲ, ŋ, ŋw, w, r, y/;

There are glaring differences in the number of Ibibio consonantal pattern. For instance, Imoh (1988) identified thirteen Ibibio consonant sounds as follows:

/p, b, t, d, m, n, ɲ, k, kp, f, s, j, w/

Essien (1990) identified sixteen Ibibio consonant sounds as follows:

/p, b, t, d, k, kp, f, s, b, m, n, ɲ, w, y/;

Urua (2000) asserts that Ibibio has twenty one consonant. These consonant sounds are classified into: six oral stops, six nasal stops, one syllabic nasal, one trill, one tap, three fricatives and three approximants. The consonant sounds according to Urua (2000) include:

/p, b, t, d, k, kp, m, /

These differences in the number of phonemic consonants of Ibibio language as Urua (2000) explains "arise partly as a result of massive overlapping found in the language depending on the position. The consonant occupies in a syllabic/word and less as a result of individual variation". Like the Ibibio consonantal inventory, differences also show in the number of the Ibibio vowel sounds in Ibibio phonemic inventory which include the short and long vowel sounds. Urua (2000) identifies sixteen vowel sounds in Ibibio phonemic inventory which include the

short and long vowel sounds. These vowel sounds as quoted from Urua (2000) include:

/i, ii, t, e, ee, a, aa, /

Whereas Essien (1990) explains that "the general Ibibio has ten vowel sounds. This he confirms was arrived at, by the Ibibio language panel of 1993 after more than six months of exhaustive deliberations. These vowel sounds as quoted from Essien (1990) include:

/i, t, u, tt, e, o, /

The above phonemic inventories reveal that there are certain sounds in French language which do not occur in Ibibio language sounds systems and vice versa. These differences in the phonemic inventories give rise to the term 'interference'.

Effects of the Differences in the Phonological Systems Errors in Pronunciation

Errors of pronunciation in spoken French have not been given attention by instructors. The speakers make a whole number of mistakes during the articulations of French words. Errors in pronunciation has been observed in articulating fricative labio - dentale voisée [f] and fricative labio – dentale voisée [v], as enunciated below:

French word	Phonetic description	French	Ibibio articulation	French speaker
Village	/vilaʃ/		/Filash/	
Victoire	/viktwaʀ/		/fiktwa/	
Vauvert	/VOVɛʀ/		/fofer/	

The errors reflected above involve the use of the voiceless labio - dental fricative /f/ which is part of the Ibibio sound system to realize and articulate or to represent /v/ the voiced counterpart which is non - existent in the Ibibio sound system. In the words: "Village, Victorie and Vauvert the voiceless labio - dental fricative /f/ is erroneously used in the place of the voiced counterpart /v/.

The erroneous substitution of sounds is observed in the use of the "consonne occlusive vélaire non voisée [k] for the consonne occlusive vélaire voisée [g]. For example:

French word	Phonetic description	French	Ibibio French speaker articulation
Garson	/gaRS/		/Kakson/
Gateau	/gato/		/kato/
Gomme	/g?m/		/k?m/

In the Ibibio sound inventory, the occlusive vélaire voisée [g] is non-existent but the occlusive vélaire non voisée [k] is available. The Ibibio French speaker therefore realizes the 'occlusive vélaire voisée" [g] as the non-voisée counterpart [k].

Speech errors are also noticeable in sounds like [j] consonne fricative palatable voisée, [ʃ] consonne fricative palatable non voisée, [z] consonne fricative apico- alvéolaire voisée. Par exemples:

French word	Phonetic description	French	Ibibio French speaker articulation
Jeune	/□/		
Jolie	//		/yoli/
Bagage			/bakash/
Chat			/shat/
Justifier			/yustifée/
Balayage			/balayash/
Chez			/shess/
Zoulou	/Zulu/		/Sulu/

From the examples, Ibibio speakers of French are seen using Ibibio palatal approximant /y/ to realized the French "fricative palatable voisée [j]. An approximate sound/s/ is also used by the Ibibio speakers of French to realized the French "fricative apico- alvéolaire voisée [z].

Errors from Dialectal Speech Habits

The Ibibio speakers of French language speak French with their dialectal speech habits. Ibibio language influences their French intonations, stress placement and realization of French phonemic sounds. The Ibibio speaker of French language often at times revert to Ibibio language rules without awareness that this phenomenon is taking place. This is why Brian Tiffen (1969) states that students have been so conditioned by the habits of their mother tongues that they cannot even hear the strange sounds of a new language, let alone produce them.

At the level of syntax, an Ibibio speaker of French language transfers the syntax of his mother tongue as a substitute for French phrases. For example:

Ibibio Phrase	Dialectal Speech Habit
1. Ami ndo isua duop – eba. (I am 12 years old)	‘Je suis douze ans’
2. M_bion andon. (I am hungry)	‘Je suis faim’.

From the above illustration, instead of saying "J'ai douze ans" and "J'ai faim", an Ibibio French speaker translates directly from Ibibio speech habit into French, "Je Suis douze ans" and "Je suis faim".

Similarity of certain sounds in the two languages is another observable feature that leads to influence of dialectal speech habits. A critical examination of French and Ibibio phonemic inventories shows that there are similar sounds which exist in the two language phonemic inventories although the articulations of these sounds are not similar. The sounds that are similar in both Ibibio and French inventories are:

CONSONANTS	VOWELS
P, b, t, d, k, f, s, m, n, ŋ, j, w, R	L, e, a, α, c, o, u, ə

An Ibibio speaker of French is faced with many problems. For instance, there is a conflict between the recognition of Ibibio sounds and its association with the correct pronunciation. There is, also, the association of alphabet Fran□ais with their correct sounds and the differentiation of similar letters with different sounds. These lead to the transfer of dialectal

speech habit to French which is the second language. From the vowel sounds of both Ibibio and French, it can be observed that every Ibibio vowel has a permanent sound which remains constant in all circumstances while it is not so in French during articulation of words containing these vowels. For instance, the /a/ in French "avion", /ävj3/ sounds differently from the /a/ in French "an" /a/ whereas in Ibibio, the /a/ in "ta" /ta/ (chew) sounds the same as in "da" /da/ (stand), (Urua, 2007).

Intonations exert influence of dialectal speech habit on the articulation of the speaker on two grounds; the person he is speaking to and the subject matter under discussion. The Ibibio speaker of French does not always consider intonation as a particularly necessary requirement in spoken French because of the tonal nature of Ibibio language.

Errors from Dialectal Orthography

French language has one alphabetical system comprising twenty-six letters, A-Z. If there was to be a one-to-one correspondence between the letters and the sounds, it would have also had twenty-six sound symbols. Curiously, the French language has about thirty-six phonetic sounds as against twenty-six letters with some of the French letters serving in dual capacities as consonants and vowels. A good example is the letter "y". This lucidly shows that there is no regular relationship between how a word is spelt in the French language and how it sounds. Therefore, to tell exactly what sounds a particular letter represents is always difficult. A single letter may have up to three or more different sounds depending on the word in which it occurs. A suitable illustration is the letter (Ee). In this letter, sounds like /e, E, ə/ may be realized in words like Père /PE:r/, été /ete/, Lẹ /Iə/ and mince /mE:s respectively.

Errors in spelling also contribute to the wrong pronunciation of many French words by Ibibio French speakers. For example;

Wrong articulations of sounds can lead to mis-pronunciation and poor performance in oral competency in the target language, and in this case, French. Speakers and learners should be taught how to make use of the dictionary for verification of words as well as their phonetic description. They should also be taught oral articulation or interpretation of words

since these words are not always pronounced as they are spelt as applicable in their mother tongue.

Orthographical errors are also observed in some homophones which have the same phonetic description and same pronunciation but different spellings ad meanings. For example, in words like;

- (1) Dans/dã/ (in)
 Dent/dã/ (tooth)
- (2) Pot/po/ (pot)
 Peau/po/ (skin)
- (3) Comte /kɜ:t/ (count)
 Conte /kɜ: t/ (story/tale)
- (4) Mai /mɛ/ (may)
 Mais /mɛ/ (but)
- (5) Cou/ku/ (neck)
 Coût/ku/ (cost)

FRENCH WORDS WRONGLY SPELT	CORRECTED VERSION
Practique	Pratique
Object	Objet
Marriage	Mariage
Adresse	Adresse
Pluspart	Plupart
Pronouncer	Prononcer

This error could be a result of influence from other languages known to the French speaker. Williams, (1990) argues that "spelling errors are caused by differences in the meaning of words in the mother-tongue and the target language". Hence, there is a tendency by the speakers to

pronounce words exactly as they are spelt. The spelling errors are sometimes caused by the similarities existing between the sounds and phonemes of the two languages in question. For instance, some Ibibio speakers of French language would pronounce /v/ as /f/ as in /vilaz/ (village), erroneously produced as /filaj/ thereby changing the morphological structure from "village" to "filash". This problem arises as a result of improper articulation of the voiced labio-dental fricative /v/. The only way to eradicate this problem is to provide the learners with enough materials on pronunciation practices by going beyond their reading texts.

Conclusion

Based on the findings of this paper, it can be concluded that Ibibio language exerts some inhibitive effects on the performance of Ibibio speakers of French Language. Thus, an Ibibio speaker of French, like any other non- native speaker of French, encounters some problems of mother tongue interferences when trying to realize words in the target language, French. This paper, therefore, suggests that efforts should be directed towards teaching and articulating the difficult and the unfamiliar sounds in French especially those that are peculiar to French and do not occur in Ibibio language to avoid wrong substitutions. Well-equipped language laboratories should be built in all learning institutions with necessary materials like vowel and consonant sounds charts as well as headphones for effective pronunciation of French words.

Instructors should endeavour to have some basic knowledge of the students' mother tongue as this would enable them easily identify the areas of interferences between the sounds of native language and French. They would, therefore, be in a better position to help students out of their problems.

Dictation exercises should be given regularly as a means of achieving oral practice and competence by the students leaning French. This would enable the students gain proficiency in the phonological and orthographical rules governing the sounds in the target language.

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